

Feasibility Assessment of 3D Neutron Flux Reconstruction in Graphite-Moderated Subcritical Assembly Core Using Multi-Material Scintillator Arrays and GEANT4

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ABSTRACT

Accurate reconstruction of spatial neutron flux distributions in subcritical reactor assemblies is essential in validating neutronics models, characterizing neutron multiplication behavior, and optimization of university level reactor research. This work investigates the feasibility of three-dimensional (3D) neutron flux mapping inside a graphite-moderated subcritical assembly through the development and simulation of a compact multi-detector system capable of measuring thermal and fast neutron fields simultaneously. An array of miniature scintillator detectors, including ⁶LiF:ZnS(Ag), HDPE+⁶LiF:ZnS(Ag), EJ-276 and CLYC, was integrated with silicon photomultipliers to enable neutron flux detection within the tight spatial constraints of the graphite lattice geometry.

A GEANT4 Monte Carlo model was constructed to evaluate detector response, optimize placement within the moderator array, and assess measurement accuracy under realistic neutron fluxes. The model incorporates physics for neutron capture, elastic scattering, scintillation light generation, and photon transport, enabling direct comparison of thermal and fast neutron detection sensitivity for different detector materials and configurations. Preliminary results demonstrate that distributed detector arrays embedded within the moderator can reproduce axial and radial flux shapes with accurate spatial resolution to support reactor physics research and education. Particularly, CLYC and EJ-276 both demonstrated strong fast neutron response and clear spectral separation, confirming their effectiveness as fast neutron scintillators in detector systems.

Keywords: Subcritical assembly, Neutron flux reconstruction, GEANT4, Scintillator, SiPM

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutrons exhibit energy-dependent interaction probabilities that strongly influence reactor physics, radiation transport behavior, and neutron-induced reaction rates. The neutron spectrum in a reactor environment typically spans fast fission energies down to a thermalized distribution, determined by scattering, moderation, and absorption processes (1; 2). Accurately characterizing this spectrum in space and energy is fundamental for reactor design, evaluating transport models, and supporting experimental validation.

In subcritical assemblies, the neutron population is maintained by an external source rather than by a self-sustaining chain reaction. The spatial flux shape depends greatly on parameters such as source placement, fuel geometry and moderator configuration (3). Measuring spatial flux distribution is essential for validating Monte Carlo neutronics models, assessing subcritical multiplication, and supporting research and instructional activities in reactor physics.

Recent developments such as the SAFFRON detector system, designed for high-resolution flux mapping in the zero-power CROCUS reactor demonstrate the feasibility and value of miniature scintillator

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based instrumentation for spatially resolved measurements in strongly moderated environments (4). These systems demonstrate that compact detector arrays can provide detailed spatial flux information while minimally disturbing the core geometry, however achieving these measurements presents unique challenges. The detector geometry must compactly fit within narrow channels in the moderator without displacing fuel. Existing miniature scintillator detectors based on ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS(Ag)}$ provide high thermal neutron sensitivity (5), but they do not additionally provide fast neutron response. This work addresses the need for an integrated, full spectrum, spatially distributed neutron detection system designed specifically for subcritical assembly research and education.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Subcritical Assembly

The first core in the proposed Ontario Tech University Subcritical Assembly (SCA) will consist of a 15×15 graphite moderator array containing natural uranium metal fuel rods, externally driven by a Deuterium-Deuterium (DD) or Deuterium-Tritium (DT) neutron generator, or radioisotope source (6). As no self-sustaining chain reaction is permitted, spatial flux measurements are essential to determine neutron moderation and leakage, evaluate spatial neutron importance and reflector effects, validate transport simulations and support instructional laboratory experiments in reactor physics. A practical flux mapping system must operate reliably within the moderator lattice, with minimal disruption of the neutron field.

2.2. Neutron Detection

Neutron detection within a reactor core involves unique processes for thermal neutrons ($<0.5\text{eV}$) and fast neutrons ($>1\text{MeV}$) (7). Among thermal neutron detection materials, ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS}$ scintillators are widely used due to their high neutron capture cross section (~ 940 barns) and large light yield (5; 8). When a neutron is captured by ${}^6\text{Li}$, an alpha particle and a triton are emitted in opposite directions according to

releasing $\sim 4.78\text{MeV}$ of kinetic energy (5). The ZnS(Ag) scintillator emits light near $\sim 450\text{nm}$, well matched to common SiPM spectral sensitivity, however self-absorption and scattering within the scintillator limit light transport efficiency (9). Incorporating a thin HDPE (High-Density Polyethylene) moderator around a ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS}$ scintillator enhances performance in mixed-energy fields by slowing fast neutrons into the thermal range, while in a strongly thermalizing graphite matrix it provides localized moderation without excessive down-scattering, consistent with polyethylene-graphite behavior (10).

Fast neutron detection typically relies on recoil rather than capture. Organic scintillators such as stilbene or EJ-276 convert neutron-proton scattering into detectable light, and their different scintillation decay components allow for pulse shape discrimination (PSD) between neutrons and gammas (11). These materials are designed to respond to MeV-scale neutrons characteristic of the upper portion of the Watt fission spectrum, although the effective interaction range in compact detector geometries may be limited by small scintillation volumes and low recoil probabilities (12). Inorganic scintillators such as CLYC-7 ($\text{Cs}_2\text{LiYCl}_6\text{:Ce}$) offer dual-mode detection, with fast neutrons interacting primarily detected via charged particle reactions on chlorine, the ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p){}^{35}\text{S}$ and ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha){}^{32}\text{P}$ reactions, producing a broad spectrum of deposited energies, while thermal neutrons are detected through the ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)$ capture reaction within the CLYC crystal lattice (12). Since the scintillators used in this work occupy small volumes, their fast-neutron interaction probability remains low compared to the strong thermal capture from surrounding materials, a known limitation of compact scintillators in moderated fields (12; 11).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Simulation Framework

To optimize detector geometry and assess feasibility for 3D neutron flux mapping, simulations were performed using GEANT4 (GEometry ANd Tracking), a Monte Carlo-based toolkit developed at CERN for simulating the passage of particles through matter (5). GEANT4 allows for detailed modeling of nuclear and optical processes, including scintillation light generation, attenuation, and reflection.

Detector configurations were modeled using GEANT4 (10), and detector placement followed a lattice distribution, enabling reconstruction of spatial flux profiles. Optical photon generation, attenuation, and SiPM detection thresholds were included as parameters to maintain realistic detection scenarios. A 14 MeV neutron source was placed in the center of the core, isotropically emitting neutrons using the G4ParticleGun class within GEANT4, for the purpose of driving neutron multiplication within the subcritical core. Parameters were chosen for alignment with future prototype testing and validation accuracy.

The physics lists chosen (13) were QGSP_BIC_HP, which provides High Precision neutron transport capabilities, and opticalPhysics, which enables realistic modeling of scintillation photon processes. QGSP_BIC_HP includes standard EM processes and uses Binary Cascade, pre-compound and various de-excitation models for hadrons, allowing for accurate detection of neutrons below 20 MeV (14), required for reactor grade neutron spectra. The addition of opticalPhysics allows GEANT4 to generate, transport, reflect, refract, and absorb individual optical photons within each scintillator, to accurately model light yield, wavelength dependent transport, surface interactions, and future wavelength shifting (WLS) fiber coupling to obtain measurable SiPM signals (13).

3.2. Reactor Geometry

The reactor core geometry was modeled in GEANT4, using parameters as close to the proposed Ontario Tech University subcritical assembly (6) as possible, to replicate realistic conditions for accurate modeling.

Figure 1. a. z-axis view of a single moderator column with cylindrical cutout for fuel rod or control rod placement, with 1mm x 2mm channels on each face centered in the x-y planes. Visible in channels are two fast (shown in teal) and two thermal (shown in pink) neutron scintillators, at varying z positions. b. 15x15 array of graphite column moderators, with either graphite control rods (blue) or natural uranium fuel rods (orange) in the respective cylindrical channels.

A 15x15 array of 10.16cm x 10.16cm x 152.4cm graphite column moderators were created, with 3.95cm x 152.4cm cylindrical cutouts in each, to accommodate either fuel rod or control rod placement. Natural uranium metal fuel was used in 16 cylindrical 3.81cm x 152.4cm aluminum clad fuel rods, which were placed within the inner most region of the modeled reactor core, with placement as seen in Figure 1b. Control rods, made from identical graphite material to the columns, filled the remaining moderators within the 15x15 array, leaving the centremost moderator empty for neutron source placement. Each moderator included a 2mm x 1mm channel cut along each face, centered in the x-y planes to create a full 2mm x 2mm channel between each moderator column, to accommodate scintillators and future WLS fibers. Two thermal and two fast detectors were placed in each channel at varying z positions, as seen in Figure 1a, to obtain an optimal neutron flux detection array within the spatial constraints.

3.3. Detector Designs

For compact detector geometries such as those considered in this work, the selection of appropriate materials and their optimization is critical in achieving effective fast neutron detection (14). Three 1.5mm x 1.5mm x 3mm scintillators were developed for fast neutron detection, one serving as a moderator coupled with a thermal neutron scintillator (HDPE+⁶LiF:ZnS, and two functioning as standalone fast neutron scintillators (EJ-276 and CLYC).

HDPE was selected for its favorable combination of long optical attenuation length and fast timing characteristics (15). In this design, a 1.5mm x 1.5mm x 2.68mm HDPE screen acts as a moderator, slowing fast neutrons toward the thermal range for capture in a 1.5mm x 1.5mm x 0.32mm ⁶LiF:ZnS scintillator positioned directly behind it. The detector response parameters adopted for the HDPE+LiF:ZnS configuration include a LiF:ZnS light yield of 50,000 photons/MeV, an optical capture efficiency of 5% (fraction of scintillation photons directed towards the WLS fibers and subsequently the silicon photomultiplier (SiPM)), and a photon detection efficiency of 25% for the SiPM (14).

EJ-276, a pulse shape discriminating plastic scintillator manufactured by Eljen Technologies, was chosen for its ability to separate gamma and fast neutron interactions through differences in scintillation decay timing (15; 8), and its proven performance in miniature fast neutron detectors (8). In this design, a 1.5mm x 1.5mm x 3mm EJ-276 screen converts incident fast neutrons into optical photons via neutron-proton scattering, enabling direct detection by the SiPM. Its emission peak near 425nm aligns well with common SiPM spectral response. Although the scintillator volume is small, the hydrogen rich polymer provides efficient recoil production for fast-neutron sensitivity. Detector parameters adopted for this design include a light yield of 9,000 photons/MeV, an optical capture efficiency of 20%, and a SiPM photon detection efficiency of 35% (15).

CLYC-7, a cerium-doped inorganic scintillator, was evaluated for its ability to detect fast neutrons over a broad energy range. The cerium dopant activator enhances scintillation efficiency and timing, enabling good light yield and pulse-shape discrimination through its fast and slow decay components (12). In this design, a 1.5mm x 1.5mm x 3mm CLYC scintillator screen converts incident fast neutrons into optical photons mainly through the ³⁵Cl(n,p)³⁵S reaction, which are then directly detected by the SiPM. Detector parameters considered for this material include a light yield of 20,000 photons/MeV (12), an optical capture efficiency of 20% (16), and a photon detection efficiency of 30% (12).

One detector configuration was developed for thermal neutron detection, lithium fluoride ⁶LiF:ZnS, based on previous success with this scintillator in miniature thermal neutron detector systems (4). In this design, a 1.5mm x 1.5mm x 0.32mm ⁶LiF:ZnS scintillator screen captures thermal neutrons and converts the reaction energy into light. Parameters considered for this detector include a light yield of 50,000 photons/MeV, an optical capture efficiency of 5%, and a photon detection efficiency of 25% (14).

For detection within the simulation, the various scintillators were directly coupled to SiPM output, however in practice wavelength shifting (WLS) fibers would be embedded within the scintillator to collect and channel scintillation light toward a SiPM photosensor.

4. RESULTS

Figure 2. a. Incident neutron energy spectra for fast neutron detectors EJ-276 and CLYC, showing the distribution of neutron kinetic energies recorded upon entering each scintillator. b. Pulse height spectra for all detector types. LiF:ZnS shows the characteristic 4.78 MeV ${}^6\text{Li}$ capture peak, while CLYC presents both fast neutron recoil features and thermal capture components and EJ-276 displays the expected wide energy recoil distribution.

Detection efficiency and response to both thermal and fast neutrons were analyzed through GEANT4 Monte Carlo simulation. These results provide the foundation for the development of a full-scale, three-dimensional neutron flux mapping system for graphite-moderated subcritical reactors, particularly for use in the proposed Ontario Tech University subcritical assembly. To obtain accurate SiPM count predictions, each scintillator's deposited energy was converted to detectable light using its material's specific light output (photons/MeV), optical transport efficiency within the geometry and the photon detection efficiency of the SiPM. This approach links neutron interaction to measurable signals, allowing for a realistic assessment of detector performance.

In the neutron energy spectra, Figure 2a, similar incident neutron energy distributions are observed for both fast neutron detectors. Within EJ-276, this behavior is characteristic of hydrogenous plastic scintillators, where n-p elastic scattering dominates and produces a continuous recoil spectrum. Similarly, the CLYC fast neutron spectrum extends across the fast neutron energy range but with slightly lower count density. This behavior arises from energy-dependent charged particle reactions, such as ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)$ and ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha)$, as well as elastic scattering, resulting in a less uniformly populated response across the fission energy range. In the PHA plot (Figure 2b), LiF:ZnS displays a narrow 4.78 MeV peak corresponding to the fixed energy deposition from the ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)t$ absorption reaction. HDPE+LiF:ZnS shows similar behavior, dominated by thermal or near-thermal interactions, but with slightly broader counts due to moderation effects and variations in interaction geometry. As expected for thermal detectors, both materials show negligible response beyond the capture peak. The EJ-276 fast plastic scintillator displays a PHA distribution across a larger energy range, and follows the expected continuous recoil spectrum. Similarly, the CLYC scintillator shows sensitivity across parts of the fast neutron range, with limitations due to its available reaction channels.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between neutron kinetic energy and SiPM photon yield for the fast neutron detectors. EJ-276 produces a gradual increase in light output with increasing neutron kinetic energy, consistent with n-p elastic recoil behavior. CLYC displays distinct banded structures corresponding to its multiple fast neutron interaction channels. This confirms the neutron to light response of these fast scintillators and highlights the contrast between recoil based and capture based detection behavior.

Figure 3. Correlation between neutron kinetic energy and scintillation light output for fast neutron detectors only (a. EJ-276 and b. CLYC). The neutron kinetic energy on the x-axis represents the GEANT4 pre-interaction energy recorded as particles enter scintillator volume. EJ-276 produces a gradual increase in light output with increasing neutron kinetic energy, characteristic of hydrogen rich plastics, while CLYC displays clear band structures associated with fast neutron interactions through $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)$.

The reconstructed 2D thermal and fast neutron flux shapes are seen in Figure 4, which were determined by the kinetic energy GEANT4 event data. The fast neutron map (Figure 4b) shows a broad smooth peak centered within the moderator array, which is the expected distribution of neutrons and their limited moderation before detection in CLYC. The thermal neutron map (Figure 4a) exhibits localized maxima and a more varied distribution, reflecting the sensitivity of thermalization within the array and the lower overall rate of thermal neutron captures in the thin LiF:ZnS screens. Together, these maps show the unique spatial behavior of fast and thermal neutrons within a graphite-moderated subcritical

Figure 4. a. 2D neutron flux maps for thermal neutrons, detected by $^6\text{LiF:ZnS}$. b. Fast neutrons, detected by CLYC. Flux maps show a normalized flux shape as the kinetic energy event rate, at each detector position divided by the maximum response within its respective detector type.

assembly and confirms this detector array captures both global and local flux features.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated compact scintillator neutron detectors for reconstructing flux distributions within a graphite-moderated subcritical assembly. GEANT4 simulations showed how detector material strongly governs energy sensitivity and scintillation behavior. The thermal detector, ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS}$, produced the expected ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha){}^3\text{H}$ capture signature and responded only to thermal neutrons. When moderated by HDPE, LiF:ZnS showed a slightly wider response but remained dominated by capture events. EJ-276 displayed fast neutron sensitivity through n-p elastic recoil, producing a broad and continuous pulse height distribution characteristic of hydrogen-rich plastic scintillators. CLYC demonstrated strong MeV features from ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p){}^{35}\text{S}$ and ${}^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha)$ interactions. The relationship between neutron kinetic energy and scintillation light output for the fast detectors, and the pulse height spectra of all materials displayed highlights the distinct interaction mechanisms and confirms that a combined thermal-fast detector lattice, particularly one incorporating ${}^6\text{LiF:ZnS}$ along with either EJ-276 or CLYC is ideal for three dimensional flux mapping and spectral characterization in subcritical assemblies.

The reconstructed thermal and fast flux maps were developed to evaluate scintillator material performance under realistic subcritical assembly conditions, while simultaneously providing spatially resolved distributions that can be compared directly with Monte Carlo neutronic predictions. Agreement in global flux shape, moderation behavior and spectral profile enables validation of both detector response modeling and core neutronics. The current detector arrangement resolves global flux structure and localized thermal effects, however finer spatial resolution may be achieved through reduced detector spacing per channel and optimized scintillator thickness. Ongoing work will assess the balance between count statistics and spatial resolution to further refine model validation capability. Future simulation work will also incorporate full pulse shape timing in GEANT4 to enable neutron/ γ discrimination and refine detector placement for improved energy coverage. Broader studies will use MCNP or OpenMC to validate flux shapes and system level neutronics, complementing the detector response modeled in GEANT4. Planned experimental work includes constructing WLS fiber coupled prototypes with SiPM readout for installation within the proposed Ontario Tech University subcritical assembly, allowing for validation of the simulated detector lattice.

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